

FAMILY OFFICES: Progress and challenges for future research. A SEW perspective

Workshop, Ourense 2018, 28 may

PURPOSE

- ▶ Define a FIBER scale for Family Offices
 - ▶ UHNW Population: growing
 - ▶ Link between business families and UHNW
 - ▶ Family office: an important instrument for wealth management
 - ▶ SEW approach applied for Family Offices
 - ▶ FIBER SCALE for Family Offices

UHNW Population

- ▶ UHNWI: a minimum of US\$ 30 million
- ▶ The UHNWI population : 226,450 individuals (2016), with total wealth of US\$ 27 trillion.
- ▶ Forecast: 299,000 people by 2021, an increase of 72,550
- ▶ Wealth: self-made, inherited/self-made or only inherited
 - ▶ In 2016, two-thirds of the fortunes of the global ultra-wealthy population were self-made.
- ▶ The origins of wealth (whether inherited or self-made) may be linked to a business family
- ▶ Private Banking versus Family Office

Family Office

- ▶ A professional organization, owned and controlled by an ultra-wealthy family. Its main function is to centralise management of the family members' fortune, and to transfer wealth and values to subsequent generations.
- ▶ ACTIVITIES
 - **Investment-related activities:**
 - asset allocation, manager selection and monitoring, investing and investment performance measurement
 - **Family-related activities:**
 - philanthropy, risk management, insurance, next generation education, concierge services and security and estate planning
 - **Administration-related:**
 - banking, financial administration, information aggregating and client reporting, legal services, technology solutions and support, trust accounting and pooled and partnership accounting
- ▶ ADVANTAGES
 - ▶ personalised service, confidentiality, control and flexibility.
 - ▶ lack of conflicting interests, a flexible structure, exclusivity and discretion.

SEW Approach

SEW refers to "non-financial aspects of the firm that meet the family's affective needs, such as identity, the ability to exercise family influence, and the perpetuation of the dynasty family" (Gómez-Mejía, Haynes, Núñez-Nickel, Jacobson & Moyano-Fuentes (2007: 106).)

FIBER Model

- ▶ F: Family control and influence
- ▶ I: Identification of family members with the firm
- ▶ B: Binding social ties
- ▶ E: Emotional attachment of family members
- ▶ R: Renewal of family bonds to the firm through dynastic succession

Family Office: a SEW perspective

- ▶ F: The control and influence of family members **OWNERSHIP ; CEO: FAM/NO FAM**
- ▶ I: close linkage between family and firm. Family ownership in a firm provides a sense of identity to the family and its members. Perceptions of identity are driven not only by the family context but also by a broader social context **EDUCATION, FINANCING
ENTREPRENEURSHIP**
- ▶ B: the firms' social relationships with various stakeholders, for example, with employees, which frequently are close and can even be family-like. Furthermore, family firms are often deeply embedded in their (local) communities, support associations, and community activities **PHILANTHROPY, FOUNDATIONS**
- ▶ E: The role of emotions in the family business context **COHESION AND HARMONY IN THE NEXT GENERATION**
- ▶ R: the long-term vision of keeping the firm under the family's control in future generations. This transgenerational vision and sense of dynasty are considered key concerns of family firms. **PRESERVE FAMILY WEALTH TO NEXT GENERATIONS (not only assets but also family values)**

FIBER SCALE

F: FAMILY CONTROL AND INFLUENCE

(Berrone et al., 2012)

F1) In my family business, family members exert control over the company's strategic decisions.

(F2) In my family business, most executive positions are occupied by family members.

(F3) In my family business, non-family managers and directors are named by family members.

(F4) The board of directors is mainly composed of family members.

(F5) The majority of the shares in my family business are owned by family members.

(F6) Preservation of family control and independence are important goals for my family business.

- (1) Family Office: >50% (family ownership)
- (2) CEO position (three binary measures: founder CEO, descendant CEO, external CEO: yes/no)
- (3) CEO duality (yes/no)
- (4) CEO stock ownership (%)
- (5) Firm age
- (6) Number of generations
- (7) Level of outsourcing services??
- (8) CORPORATE GOVERNANCE: Family Council /Board

FIBER SCALE

I: IDENTIFICATION OF FAMILY MEMBERS WITH THE FIRM (Berrone et al., 2012)

(I1) Family members have a strong sense of belonging to my family business

(I2) Family members feel that the family business's success is their own success.

(I3) My family business has a great deal of personal meaning for family members.

(I4) Being a member of the family business helps define who we are.

(I5) Family members are proud to tell others that we are part of the family business.

(I6) Customers often associate the family name with the family business's products and services.

- EDUCATION programs for becoming good owners
- FINANCING ENTREPRENEURSHIP

FIBER SCALE

B: BINDING SOCIAL TIES (Berrone et al., 2012)

(B1) My family business is very active in promoting social activities at the community level.

(B2) In my family business, non-family employees are treated as part of the family.

(B3) In my family business, contractual relationships are mainly based on trust and norms of reciprocity.

(B4) Building strong relationships with other institutions (i.e., other companies, professional associations, government agents, etc.) is important for my family business.

(B5) Contracts with suppliers are based on enduring long-term relationships in my family business

(1) Family Office manages Family Foundation :
yes/no

(2) Family Office manages philanthropic activities:
yes/no

(3) Family Office finances internal entrepreneurial activities: yes/no

FIBER SCALE

E: EMOTIONAL ATTACHMENT OF FAMILY MEMBERS (Berrone et al., 2012)

(E1) Emotions and sentiments often affect decision-making processes in my family business.

(E2) Protecting the welfare of family members is critical to us, apart from personal contributions to the business.

(E3) In my family business, the emotional bonds between family members are very strong.

(E4) In my family business, affective considerations are often as important as economic considerations.

(E5) Strong emotional ties among family members help us maintain a positive self-concept.

(E6) In my family business, family members feel warmth for each other.

(1) Family Office prepares annual family meetings: yes/no

(2) Family Office organizes educational programs for family members: yes/no

(3) Number of family branches:

(4) Number of family members belonging to the Family Office

FIBER SCALE

R: RENEWAL OF FAMILY BONDS THROUGH
DYNASTIC SUCCESSION (Berrone et al.,
2012)

(R1) Continuing the family legacy and tradition is an important goal for my family business.

(R2) Family owners are less likely to evaluate their investment on a short-term basis.

(R3) Family members would be unlikely to consider selling the family business.

(R4) Successful business transfer to the next generation is an important goal for family members

(1) Continuing the family legacy and tradition is an important goal for my family office: yes/no

(2) Using a Likert scale, Which are the main goals of your family office?

- Family cohesion
- Education
- Confidentiality
- Independent management
- Philanthropy
- Achieve better lifestyle
- Better management of family issues